

Gender Difference and Cyber Communication; Internet and Social Media Usage Pattern of Universities Students

Asghar Ullah Khan* Muhammad Saqib Khan† Afshan Jabeen‡

Vol. III, No. I (2018)

Pages: 8 – 18

DOI: 10.31703/gesr.2018(III-I).02

Abstract: *The main objective of the research study was to know the usage pattern of cyber communication by the universities students of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP). It was a descriptive and survey analytical research. The population of the study was all universities students of KP. 800 students were selected from 6 universities of KP. The collected data were processed, tabulated, explained and interpreted through some statistical tools i.e. tables, percentages and t-test. The major findings showed that university students are regular users of cyber communication. Most of them use internet and social media (SM) more than two hours per day. A big chunk of the university students uses it for the education and entertainment purposes. The findings also revealed that there is a difference between genders in using cyber communication. In the light of the said findings, certain major recommendations were made in order to achieve the maximum benefits of the study.*

Key Words: Gender Difference, Cyber Communication, Internet, Social Media, Usage Pattern University Students

Introduction

Cyber communication technology plays a very significant role in self-expression. Young generation uses these technologies as an experiment for the recognition of their political views, social status, ethnic ideas, and cultural and sexual identity. These technologies provide a forum to their users to get themselves engaged in sharing their political, social and general ideas with likeminded people. Such users utilize e-mail, users generated content, chat rooms, online pages and other social networking services (Collin et al. 2011, Montgomery 2009, Vromen 2007, 2008). By using social networking sites, individual have got an easy access to interact closely with one another. Warschauer (1997) noted “this new technology bridges the historic divide between speech and writing”. Due to the boom of the Internet a considerable concern has arisen over research in this field.

Joseph Walther in 1992 developed Social Information Processing Theory (SIP), which deals with interpersonal communication and belongs to the concerns of media study. SIP theory elucidates the interpersonal communication performed online without nonverbal cues, and it also explains how people develop and manage their interactions in a computer-mediated environment (Walther 2015). While Computer Mediated Communication (CMC) also defines human communication that is not possible without electronic devices. McQuail (2005) noted that CMC is performed through computer-mediated patterns (e.g. chat rooms, email, instant messaging, social networking sites, online forums), CMC has also been applied to other patterns of information that are based upon text, such as text messaging. It is powerful enough to overcome other limitations e.g. physical and social, and allows people to make an interaction even not being present at the same space.

Computer-mediated environment needs more time to develop effective interpersonal communication, on the other hand a face to face communication does not consume so much time in developing an interpersonal relationship. Jarvenpaa, Knoll, and Leidner (1998) noted that SIP theory explains the dimensions and qualities which play their role in both, computer-mediated communication

*Advocate, Department of Communication and Media studies, Gomal University, D.I.K, KP, Pakistan.

†Lecturer, Department of Business Administration, Gomal University, Dera Ismail Khan, KP, Pakistan.
Email: saqiblecturer@gmail.com

‡ PhD Scholar, Department of Sports Sciences, Gomal University, Dera Ismail Khan, KP, Pakistan.

and face to face relationship. The online interactions are more helpful to facilitate relationships that could never happen in face to face interactions due to geographical limitations and intergroup anxiety. Joseph Walther (1992) noted that the theory concentrates upon the social processes that happen when two or more individuals get themselves engaged in communication ([Walther 2015](#)).

The Internet technology has revolutionized communications world and gave new look to interpersonal communication. The Internet has enormously augmented the capability of individuals to meet, interact, and connect with whom they share something in common, regardless of demographic or terrestrial restrictions ([Kabir 2018](#)).

The internet was made available in Pakistan since early 90s. The individuals of all ages have been revolutionized by the digital age to interact through various networking sites, such as Tumbler, Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp etc. Why these networking sites are becoming more and more popular among the generations is due to their unique quality of being easily accessible to every individual. Moreover, these sites provide cheaper and more effective means of communication. Furthermore, increase in smartphone usage has also increased the reach of individuals to the use internet. Keeping in view the importance of this new technology, present studies focus on the internet and social media usage pattern of male and female university students. University students are expected to be the regular internet users and of social media (SM) for the purposes of entertainment, information, education and time passing. In the present study a difference between gender of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) Universities about their internet and social media usage pattern. This internet usage pattern includes daily and weekly time spending on using internet, sources and purpose of using internet by the KP university students and guardianship monitoring. While social media (SM) usage pattern includes, frequency of using SM, online apps, SM activities, sharing personal information, sharing/forwarding political and social information and guardianship restrictions.

Objectives of The Study

For the current study three main objectives were formulated:

1. To explore the Internet usage pattern i.e., daily and weekly time spending on using internet, sources and purpose of using internet by the KP university youth and guardianship monitoring.
2. To explore the social media usage pattern i.e., frequency of using SM, online apps, SM activities, sharing personal information, sharing/forwarding political and social information and guardianship restrictions.
3. To investigate the usage of cyber communication by the male and female youth of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Methodology

Every researcher uses a particular procedure to execute the research plan. This study adopted cross-sectional survey research method to explore the phenomenon, and the sample of 800 students was selected using a Multi-stage sampling method. The sample is carefully chosen on the basis of their gender according to their proportion from six highest ranking universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) ([UniRank 2017](#)) ranked by HEC. KP is one of the four administrative provinces of Pakistan. A close-ended questionnaire for measuring the concepts of the study was used and distributed among the selected sample. All the KP university youth were included in the population of the present study and youth of KP are the unit of analysis. The universe of the study is the youth community of KP studying at under graduate, graduate and post graduate level in various educational institutions of KP Pakistan.

Internet Usage Pattern

By Internet usage Pattern means daily and weekly time spending on using internet by the students, from which device students use internet (Personal smartphone, parents mobile, friends mobile, home PC, internet café etc.) and for what purpose they use internet (education, entertainment, time passing).

Whether the university students use internet in the presence of their guardian or monitored by the guardian.

Social media (SM) Usage Pattern

Pattern of SM means frequency of using SM, online apps, SM activities, sharing personal information, sharing/forwarding political and social information and guardianship restrictions.

Hypotheses

H₁-There is a significant difference between male and female university youth to their use of Cyber Communication.

H₀-There is no significant difference between male and female university youth to their use of Cyber Communication

Data Analysis

Cross Tabulation of Internet Usage Pattern

Table 1. Daily Hours Spending on using Internet by the Gender of KP Universities.

Gender	Less than 2 hrs	2 to 4 hrs	more than 4 hrs
Male	148 (24.62%)	297 (49.41%)	156(25.95%)
Female	50(25.12%)	93(46.73%)	56(28.14%)

The above table no1 shows Daily Hours spending on using internet by the male and female students of KP universities, less than two hours, 2 to 4 hours, more than 4 hours. Table shows above 40% male and female use internet 2 to 4 hours daily.

Table 2. Per-Week USAGE of Internet by the Gender of KP Universities

Gender	1 day	2 days	3 days	Every day	Don't Know
Male	20 (3.33%)	34 (5.65%)	57 (9.48%)	445 (74.04%)	45 (7.48%)
Female	6 (3.01%)	21 (10.55%)	9 (4.52%)	153 (76.88%)	10 (5.02%)

The above table shows the per week usage of internet by the male and female students of KP universities i.e., One day, two days, three days, every day, don't know. Table shows that a huge number 74.04% males and 76.88% females use internet every day.

Table 3. Usage of Internet through Different Devices by the Gender of KP Universities

	Gender	Very Often	Sometimes	Never
Personal phone	Male	413(68.71%)	133(22.12%)	55(9.15%)
	Female	142(71.35%)	40(20.10%)	17(8.54%)
Parents Mobile	Male	17(2.82%)	174(28.95%)	410(68.21%)
	Female	12(6.03%)	58(29.14%)	129(64.82%)
Friends Mobile	Male	18(2.99%)	240(39.93%)	343(57.07%)
	Female	8(4.02%)	91(45.72%)	100(50.25%)
Home PC/ Laptop	Male	187(31.11%)	247(41.09%)	167(27.78%)
	Female	66(33.16%)	94(47.23%)	39(19.59%)
Internet Café	Male	24(3.99%)	179(29.78%)	398(66.22%)
	Female	4(2.01%)	69(34.67%)	126(63.31%)
Office/University Computer	Male	39(6.48%)	200(33.27%)	362(60.23%)
	Female	15(7.53%)	71(35.67%)	113(56.78%)
Friends Computer	Male	19(3.16 %)	188(31.28%)	394(65.55%)
	Female	12(6.03%)	66(33.16%)	121(60.80%)

The above table displays the devices through which internet is used by the male and female universities student i.e., through Personal smartphone, parents mobile, friends mobile, home PC/Laptop, internet cafe, Office/University computer, friends compute. Table shows that a huge number 68.71% of males and 71.35% of females use internet through their smartphones very often. It is also revealed in the table that a huge percentage of males 68.21% and females 64.82% never use internet through their parents' mobile. While 57.07% of males and 50.25% of females never use internet through their friends' mobile and only 39.93% of males and 45.72% of females use internet sometimes through their friends' mobile. 41.09% males and 47.23% of females use internet sometimes through their home pc/laptop and only 31.11% of males and 33.16% of females very often use internet through their home pc/laptop. Table no 3 shows that above 50 % of males and females never use internet through internet café or through office/university computer and friends' computer.

Table 4. Purpose of Using Internet by The Gender of KP Universities

	Gender	Very Frequently	Sometimes	Never
Information	Male	374(62.22%)	196(32.61%)	31(5.15%)
	Female	126(63.31%)	69(34.67%)	4(2.01%)
Entertainment	Male	285(47.42%)	288(47.92%)	28(4.65%)
	Female	106(53.26%)	86(43.21%)	7(3.51%)
Education	Male	390(64.89%)	193(32.11%)	18(2.99%)
	Female	126(63.31%)	66(33.16%)	7(3.51%)
Passing time	Male	220(36.60%)	285(47.42%)	96(15.97%)
	Female	71(35.67%)	108(54.27%)	20(10.05%)

Table 4 indicates the gender-wise purpose of using internet in KP universities. It shows that above 60 % of males and females very frequently use internet for information and educational purpose. 47.42% of males and 53.26% of females very frequently use internet for entertainment purpose. While 36.60% of males and 35.67% of females very frequently use internet for passing their time.

Table 5. Frequency of using Internet by the Gender of KP Universities under Guardianship.

	Gender	Very Often	Sometimes	Never
Parents	Male	70(11.64%)	320(53.24%)	211(35.10%)
	Female	32(16.08%)	113(56.78%)	54(27.13%)
Friends	Male	324(53.91%)	229(38.10%)	48(7.98%)
	Female	111(55.77%)	71(35.67%)	17(8.54%)
Teacher/ Counsellor	Male	41(6.82%)	290(48.25%)	270(44.92%)
	Female	17(8.54%)	98(49.24%)	84(42.21%)
Siblings	Male	160(26.62%)	266(44.25%)	175(29.11%)
	Female	76(38.19%)	69(34.67%)	54(27.13%)
Someone else	Male	150(24.95%)	293(48.75%)	158(26.28%)
	Female	60(30.15%)	85(42.71%)	54(27.13%)
No One	Male	342(56.90%)	129(21.46%)	130(21.63%)
	Female	113(56.78%)	47(23.61%)	39(19.59%)

Table no 5 explains the frequency of using internet by the gender of KP universities under guardianship (Parents, friends, teacher/counsellor, siblings, someone else, no one). Table shows that above 50 % males and females sometimes use internet in the presence of parents. While 35.10% of males and 27.13% of females never use internet in the presence of parents. 53.91% of males and 55.77% of females very often use internet in the presence of friends while 38.10% of males and 35.67% of females sometimes use internet in the presence of friends. The table also shows that 48.25% of males and 49.24% of females sometimes use internet in the presence of teacher/counselor. 44.92% of males and 42.21% of females never use internet in the presence of teacher/counselor. 44.25% of males and 34.67% of females sometimes use internet in the presence of siblings. 29.11% of males never use mobile in the presence of siblings while and 38.19% of females very often use internet in the presence of siblings. 48.75% of males

and 42.71% of females sometimes use internet in the presence of someone else while above 50% of males and females very often use internet in the presence of no one.

Table 6. Gender Internet usage Monitored by the Guardians

	Gender	Very Often	Sometimes	Never
Parents	Male	83(13.81%)	274(45.59%)	244(40.59%)
	Female	30(15.07%)	101(50.75%)	68(34.17%)
Friends	Male	126(20.96%)	327(54.40%)	148(24.62%)
	Female	59(29.64%)	100(50.25%)	40(20.10%)
Teacher/Counsellor	Male	78(12.97%)	252(41.93%)	271(45.09%)
	Female	24(12.06%)	88(44.22%)	87(43.71%)
Siblings	Male	77(12.81%)	275(45.75%)	249(41.43%)
	Female	25(12.56%)	96(48.24%)	78(39.19%)
Someone else	Male	52(8.65%)	252(41.93%)	297(49.41%)
	Female	20(10.05%)	93(46.73%)	86(43.21%)
No One	Male	42(6.98%)	94(15.64%)	465(77.37%)
	Female	19(9.54%)	24(12.06%)	156(78.39%)

The above table 6 shows gender internet usage monitor by the guardians (Parents, Friends, Teacher/Counsellor, Siblings, Someone else, and No One). The table shows that 45.59% males are sometimes monitored by their parents while 50.75% female are sometimes monitored by their parents. 40.59% males are never monitored by their parents while 34.17% female are never monitored by their parents. Table no 6 also shows that above 50% males and females are sometimes monitored by their friends. Almost equal percentage of male and female never monitored by their teacher/counselor i.e., 45.09% and 43.71% male and female respectively. 45.75% males are sometimes monitored by their siblings while 48.24% female are sometimes monitored by their siblings. It is interesting to note that above 70% males and females are never monitored by no one.

Social Media usage Pattern

Table 7. Social Media use by the Gender of KP Universities

	Gender	Very Frequently	Sometimes	Never
Facebook	Male	354(58.90%)	213(35.44%)	34(5.65%)
	Female	122(61.30%)	63(31.65%)	14(7.03%)
Instagram	Male	96(15.97%)	233(38.76%)	272(45.25%)
	Female	35(17.58%)	85(42.71%)	79(39.69%)
LinkedIn	Male	53(8.81%)	172(28.61%)	376(62.56%)
	Female	21(10.55%)	47(23.61%)	131(65.82%)
Twitter	Male	143(23.79%)	181(30.11%)	277(46.08%)
	Female	55(27.63%)	52(26.13%)	92(46.23%)
WhatsApp	Male	365(60.73%)	184(30.61%)	52(8.65%)
	Female	126(63.31%)	53(26.63%)	20(10.05%)
YouTube	Male	339(56.40%)	218(36.27%)	44(7.32%)
	Female	125(62.81%)	59(29.64%)	15(7.53%)
Any Other	Male	80(13.31%)	191(31.78%)	330(54.90%)
	Female	29(14.57%)	78(39.19%)	92(46.23%)

The above table indicates the gender-wise frequency of using different social networking platforms, Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, Twitter, WhatsApp, YouTube, in KP universities. It shows that an above 50% of males and 60% of females use Facebook very frequently. While 35.44% of males and 31.65% of females sometimes use Facebook. 38.76% of males and 42.71% of females sometimes use Instagram. 28.61% of males and 23.61% of females sometimes use LinkedIn. 46.08% of males and 46.23% of females sometimes use twitter. Table also shows that a huge number 60.73% of males and 63.31% of females very frequently use WhatsApp. While 30.61% of males and 26.63% of females sometimes use WhatsApp.

56.40% of males and 62.81% of females very frequently use YouTube. 39.19% of males and 33.62% of females very frequently use other social networking platform.

Table 8. Usage of Online Application by the Gender of KP Universities

	Gender	V Frequently	Sometimes	Never
Email	Male	152(25.29%)	356(59.23%)	93(15.47%)
	Female	59(29.64%)	112(56.28%)	28(14.07%)
Instant-Messaging	Male	231(38.43%)	187(31.11%)	183(30.44%)
	Female	79(39.69%)	67(33.66%)	53(26.63%)
Messenger	Male	321(53.41%)	220(36.60%)	60(9.98%)
	Female	113(56.78%)	71(35.67%)	15(7.53%)
Chat Room	Male	29(4.82%)	112(18.63%)	469(78.03%)
	Female	14(7.03%)	35(17.58%)	158(79.39%)
WhatsApp	Male	363(60.39%)	188(31.28%)	50(8.31%)
	Female	133(66.83%)	51(25.62%)	15(7.53%)
Any Other	Male	54(8.98%)	178(29.61%)	369(61.39%)
	Female	18(9.04%)	64(32.16%)	117(58.79%)

The above table no 8 shows the frequency of using different online applications, Email, Instant-Messaging, Messenger, Chat room, WhatsApp, Any other by the genders of KP universities. Table shows that 59.23% males and 56.28% females sometimes use Email and 25.29% males and 29.64% females very frequently use Email. 38.43% males and 29.69% females very frequently use Instant Messaging. 53.41% males and 56.78% females very frequently use Messenger and only 36.60% males and 35.67% females sometimes use Messenger. 18.63% males and 17.58% females sometimes use Chat room. Above 60% males and females very frequently use WhatsApp. 61.39% males and 58.79% females never use any other online application.

Table 9. Usage of SM Activities by the Gender of KP Universities

	Gender	V Frequently	Sometimes	Never
Post	Male	182(30.28%)	351(58.40%)	68(11.31%)
	Female	58(29.14%)	116(58.29%)	25(12.56%)
Comments	Male	227(37.77%)	328(54.57%)	40(6.65%)
	Female	91(45.72%)	93(46.73%)	15(7.53%)
Forward	Male	161(26.78%)	323(53.74%)	117(19.46%)
	Female	53(26.63%)	100(50.25%)	46(23.11%)
Like	Male	345(57.40%)	206(34.27%)	50(8.31%)
	Female	120(60.30%)	69(34.67%)	10(5.02%)
Unlike	Male	81(13.47%)	320(53.24%)	199(33.11%)
	Female	28(14.07%)	103(51.75%)	68(34.17%)
Friend Request	Male	146(24.29%)	393(65.39%)	62(10.31%)
	Female	38(19.09%)	130(65.32%)	31(15.57%)
Unfriend	Male	89(14.80%)	399(66.38%)	143(23.79%)
	Female	25(12.56%)	131(65.82%)	43(21.60%)
Mark Private	Male	119(19.80%)	260(43.26%)	222(36.93%)
	Female	41(20.60%)	95(47.73%)	63(31.65%)
Mark Public	Male	126(20.96%)	257(42.76%)	218(36.27%)
	Female	48(24.12%)	91(45.72%)	60(30.15%)
Tagging	Male	97(16.13%)	330(54.90%)	174(28.95%)
	Female	40(20.10%)	108(54.27%)	51(25.62%)
Follow	Male	122(20.29%)	364(60.56%)	115(19.13%)
	Female	32(16.08%)	121(60.80%)	46(23.11%)
Unfollow	Male	56(9.31%)	341(56.73%)	204(33.94%)
	Female	14(7.03%)	116(58.29%)	69(34.67%)

Poke	Male	39(6.48%)	239(39.76%)	323(53.74%)
	Female	14(7.03%)	86(43.21%)	99(49.74%)
Others	Male	25(4.15%)	196(32.61%)	380(63.22%)
	Female	11(5.52%)	67(33.66%)	121(60.80%)

The above table no 9 explains the frequency of using different SM activities, Post, comments, forward, like, unlike, friend request, unfriend, mark private, mark public, tagging, follow, unfollow, poke, others by the genders of KP Universities. Table shows that almost equal percentage of males 58.40% and females 58.29% post sometimes while 30.28% males and 29.14% females very frequently post. 54.57% males and 46.73% females sometimes comments while 37.77% males and 45.72% females very frequently comments on online. A huge number of males 53.74% and females 50.25% sometimes use the online activity of forward. 57.40% males and 60.30% females very frequently use the online activity of like while 53.24% males and 51.75% females very frequently use the unlike activity. Table also reveals that a big and equal chunk of males 65.39% and females 65.32% sometimes use the online activity of friend request while only 24.29% males and 19.09% females very frequently use friend request activities. 66.38% males and 65.82% females sometimes use unfriend activity. 23.79% males and 21.60% females never use the unfriend activity. The above table no 9 shows that 43.26% males and 47.73% females sometimes mark private while 36.93% males and 31.65% females never mark private. 42.76% males and 45.72% females sometimes mark public activity. 36.27% males and 30.15% females never mark public activity. Above 50% males and females sometimes use tagging. While 28.95% males and 25.62% females never tagging. 60.56% males and 60.80% females sometimes use follow activities while 19.13% males and 23.11% females never use follow activity. And a huge number 56.73% males and 58.29% females sometimes use unfollow activity. 33.94% males and 34.67% females never use unfollow activity. The above table explains that 53.74% males and 49.74% females never use 'poke' activity while 39.76% males and 43.21% females sometimes use 'poke' activity. The above table also shows that a huge number 63.22% males and 60.80% females never use other online activities.

Table 10. Sharing Personal Information on SM by the Gender Of KP Universities

	Gender	Very Often	Sometimes	Never
Age	Male	143(23.79%)	305(50.74%)	153(25.45%)
	Female	59(29.64%)	97(48.74%)	43(21.60%)
Gender	Male	237(39.43%)	257(42.76%)	107(17.80%)
	Female	80(40.20%)	86(43.21%)	30(15.07%)
Picture	Male	234(38.93%)	305(50.74%)	62(10.31%)
	Female	80(40.20%)	86(43.21%)	33(16.58%)
Phone Number	Male	103(17.13%)	241(40.09%)	257(42.76%)
	Female	31(15.57%)	73(36.68%)	95(47.73%)
School Information	Male	184(30.61%)	307(51.08%)	110(18.30%)
	Female	58(29.14%)	105(52.76%)	36(18.09%)
Extracurricular Activities	Male	165(27.45%)	288(47.92%)	148(24.62%)
	Female	62(31.15%)	93(46.73%)	44(22.11%)
Goals	Male	146(24.29%)	285(47.42%)	170(28.28%)
	Female	53(26.63%)	89(44.72%)	57(28.64%)
Emotional Distress	Male	91(15.14%)	261(43.42%)	249(41.43%)
	Female	32(16.08%)	87(43.71%)	80(40.20%)
Family Conflicts	Male	27(4.49%)	163(27.12%)	411(68.38%)
	Female	8(4.02%)	53(26.63%)	138(69.34%)
Description of Yourself	Male	107(17.80%)	309(51.41%)	185(30.78%)
	Female	45(22.61%)	89(45.40%)	65(32.66%)
Audio	Male	47(7.82%)	297(49.41%)	257(42.76%)
	Female	20(10.05%)	97(48.74%)	82(41.20%)
Video	Male	113(18.80%)	321(53.41%)	167(27.78%)
	Female	40(20.10%)	93(46.73%)	66(33.16%)

The above table no 10 explains the frequency of sharing personal information (age, gender, picture, phone number, school information, extracurricular activities, goals, emotional distress, family conflicts, description of yourself, audio, video, any other) on SM by the gender of KP universities. Table shows that 50.74% males and 48.74% females sometimes share their personal information of age on SM and 25.45% males never share the personal information of age while 29.64% females very often share the personal information of age on SM. 42.76% males and 43.21% females sometimes share their gender information while 39.43% males and 40.20% females very often share their gender information on SM. 50.74% males and 43.21% females sometimes share pictures on SM. While 38.93% males and 40.20% females very often share picture on SM. 42.76% males and 47.73% females never share phone number on SM 40.09% males and 36.68% females sometimes share phone number on SM. 51.08% males and 52.76% females sometimes share school information .47.92% males and 46.73% females sometimes share extracurricular activities on SM. 47.42% males and 44.72% females sometimes share their goals on SM. 43.42% males and 43.71% females sometimes share their emotional distress on SM. 68.38% males and 69.34% females never share their family conflicts on SM. While only 27.12% males and 26.63% females sometimes share their family conflicts on SM. Above 45% males and females sometimes share their self-description, audio and video on SM.

Table 11. Guardian Restriction on SM by the Gender of KP Universities

Restrictions	Gender	Very Often	Sometimes	Never
SM use only Specific days of the Week	Male	71(11.81%)	188(31.28%)	342(56.90%)
	Female	17(8.54%)	70(35.17%)	112(56.28%)
Use only recommended websites	Male	99(16.47%)	240(39.93%)	262(43.59%)
	Female	27(13.56%)	73(36.68%)	99(49.74%)
Using filtering soft wares for unwanted material	Male	112(18.63%)	162(26.95%)	327(54.40%)
	Female	41(20.60%)	52(26.13%)	106(53.26%)
Regularly checking visited websites	Male	42(6.98%)	178(29.61%)	381(63.39%)
	Female	16(8.04%)	43(21.60%)	140(70.35%)

The above table no 11 shows guardian restriction on online activities by using following measures, Only Specific days of the Week, To use recommended websites, Using filtering software's to protect from unwanted material, Regularly checking the visited websites. Table shows that 56.90% males never restricted by guardian to use internet on the specific days of the week while 56.28% female are never restricted by guardian to use internet on the specific days of the week. 43.59% males never restricted by guardian to use recommended websites while 49.74% female are never restricted by guardian to use recommended websites. 54.40% males are never restricted by guardian Using filtering software's to protect them from unwanted material while 53.26% female are never restricted by guardian Using filtering software's to protect them from unwanted material. 63.39% males are never restricted by guardian by regularly checking the visited website while 70.35% female are never restricted by guardian by regularly checking the websites they visited.

Table 12. Sharing/ Forwarded Material for others to read on SM by the Gender of KP Universities

Forwarded material	Gender	V. frequently	Sometimes	Never
Political Issues	Male	51(8.48%)	281(46.75%)	269(44.75%)
	Female	22(11.05%)	83(41.70%)	94(47.23%)
Links to articles on Social issues	Male	81(13.47%)	383(63.72%)	137(22.79%)
	Female	31(15.57%)	119(59.79%)	49(24.62%)
Own thoughts or comments on political issues	Male	74(12.31%)	266(44.25%)	261(43.42%)
	Female	21(10.55%)	91(45.72%)	87(43.71%)
Own thoughts or comments on Social issues	Male	156(25.95%)	315(52.41%)	130(21.63%)
	Female	49(24.62%)	111(55.77%)	39(19.59%)
Encourage others to take action on Social issue that is important to you	Male	89(14.80%)	300(49.91%)	212(35.27%)
	Female	30(15.07%)	84(42.21%)	85(42.71%)

The above table no 12 shows sharing/ forwarded material for others to read on SM by the Gender of KP Universities i.e., forwarded material for others to use, political issues, links to articles on social issues, own thoughts or comments on political issues, own thoughts or comments on social issues, encourage others to take action on political and social issue that is important to you, encourage others to take action on issue that is important to you. Table shows that 44.75% males never use SM to share political issues for others to read while 47.23 females never use SM to share political issues for others to read. 63.72% males sometimes use social media to share articles links on social issues for others to read while 59.79 females sometimes use SM to share articles links on social issues for others to read while 22.79% males never use SM to share articles links on social issues for others to read while 24.62 females never use SM to share articles links on social issues for others to read. Table no 12 reveals that 44.25% males sometimes use SM to share own thoughts or comments on political issues for others to read while 45.72 females sometimes use SM to share own thoughts or comments on political issues for others to read. 43.42% males never use SM to share own thoughts or comments on political issues for others to read while 43.71 females never use SM to share own thoughts or comments on political issues for others to read. 52.41% males sometimes use SM to share own thoughts or comments on social issues for others to read while 55.77 females sometimes use SM to share own thoughts or comments on social issues for others to read. 25.95% males very frequently use SM to share own thoughts or comments on social issues for others to read while 24.62 females very frequently use SM to share own thoughts or comments on social issues for others to read. 49.91% males sometimes use SM to encourage others to take action on political issue that is important to them while 42.21 females sometimes use SM to encourage others to take action on political issue that is important to them. 35.27% males never use SM to encourage others to take action on political issue that is important to them while 42.71 females never use SM to encourage others to take action on political issue that is important to them. 45.75% males sometimes use social media to encourage others to take action on social issue that is important to them while 48.24 females sometimes use SM to encourage others to take action on social issue that is important to them. 28.61% males never use SM to encourage others to take action on Social issue that is important to them while only 26.63 females very frequently use SM to encourage others to take action on social issue that is important to them.

Table 13. T-Test to Compare Means Difference of Six Leading KP Universities Students Using Cyber Communication

Groups	N	Mean	SD	CV	Df	A	t-value	t-tabulated
Male	601	100.16	106.73	106.55	10	0.05	5.02	1.812
Female	199	33.16	45.23	136.39				

The results indicate N, mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variance, degree of freedom, alpha, t-tabulated and t-calculated of cyber communication by the male and female students of six leading KP universities. The mean of male students was 100.16 higher than the mean score of female 33.16. SD in the score of two groups, male and female was 106.73 and 45.23 respectively. The obtained T-calculated value 5.02 is greater than the t-tabulated 1.812 so we reject H_0 and accept H_1 . It is concluded that there is a significant difference between male and female in their cyber communication. The coefficient of variance

(CV) of male is lower 106.55 than the CV of female 136.39. The less value of CV shows the consistency of using Cyber Communication by the male of six leading universities of KP. It is significant at 0.05 level.

Conclusion

The present study deals with the title 'Gender difference and cyber communication; internet and social media usage pattern of university students (a case study of six leading universities of KP). For the study three main objectives were formulated, to explore the Internet usage pattern i.e., daily and weekly time spending on using internet, sources and purpose of using internet by the KP university students and guardianship monitoring, to explore the social media usage pattern i.e., frequency of using SM, online apps, SM activities, sharing personal information, sharing /forwarding political and social information and guardianship restrictions and to know the difference between gender demographic characteristics of university students of KP and their use of cyber communication. Its main focus was on the internet and social media usage pattern by the University student of KP. To find out the difference between male and female university students using internet and social media under the ambit of cyber communication. The data was collected from the 800 specified questionnaires distributed among the male and female students of six leading universities of KP, Khyber Medical University Peshawar, University of Peshawar, Agriculture University Peshawar, Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan, University of Engineering and Technology Peshawar and Gomal University, Dera Ismail Khan. The data was analyzed by SPSS 21.0. Statistical t-test was used to investigate mean difference between the research variables. This statistical evidence further proved our given hypotheses. Cross tabulation and frequency distribution of the demographic variable of gender on internet and social media usage pattern showed that both male and female universities students daily spend 2 to 4 hours on using internet. It is interesting to note that mostly use internet from their own mobile and most of the students never use internet from their parents mobile. It is also interesting to note that university students very frequently use internet for information and educational purpose. They use internet in the presence of their guardians (parents, friends, teachers) and their guardians monitor them. As for as social media use age pattern is concerned both male and female use almost all the social media and all its applications. University students mostly use FB and WhatsApp for using different online activities, post, comments, forward, like, unlike, friend request, unfriend, mark private, mark public, tagging, follow, unfollow, poke.

They also use it for sharing personal information, political and social information. It is concluded that there is a significant difference between male and female of using cyber communication. We reject H_0 and accept H_1 . The coefficient of variance (CV) of males is lower than the CV of females the less value of CV shows the consistency of using internet by the male of six leading universities of KP.

Policy Implications and Research Suggestions

Social media and internet have become the major source of education, information and entertainment. The new generations utilize internet mostly merely for socialization, by following the findings of the present study it would become more practical to encourage the young to utilize the network for fruitful purposes besides socialization purposes.

Awareness raising seminars should be held regularly at educational institutions to give up-to-date knowledge

Close relatives should be more vigilant about all the online activities of their children. Instead of relying on measuring perceptions of the victims, future research should focus on measuring the effects directly through recording the instances where government surveillance has affected people's online freedom of expression.

As this study was limited to few universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province of Pakistan, studies with same variables can be carried out in other areas of the country.

There is a space enough for future researchers in this area by providing them a wider age range and different geographical locations.

Cyber communication is a new phenomenon. Still there are different dimensions to explore for future researchers.

References

- Collin, et. al. (2011). "The benefits of social networking services."
- Jarvenpaa, et. al. (1998). "Is anybody out there? Antecedents of trust in global virtual teams." *Journal of management information systems*,14 (4): 29-64.
- Kabir, R. (2018). "Does the addiction in online pornography affect the behavioral pattern of undergrad private university students in Bangladesh?".
- McQuail, D. (2005). "McQuail" s." *Mass Communication Theory*.
- Montgomery, Kathryn C. (2009). *Generation digital: Politics, commerce, and childhood in the age of the Internet*: MIT press.
- UniRank. (2017). *Khyber Pakhtunkhwa University Ranking 2017* [cited December 6 2017]. Available from <https://www.4icu.org/pk/khyber-pakhtunkhwa/>.
- Vromen, A. (2007). "Australian young people's participatory practices and internet use." *Information, Community & Society*, 10 (1): 48-68.
- Vromen, A. (2008). "Inclusion through voice: youth participation in government and community decision-making."
- Walther, J., B. (2015). "Social Information Processing Theory (CMC)." *The International Encyclopedia of Interpersonal Communication*: 1-13.
- Mark, W. (1997). "Computer-mediated collaborative learning: Theory and practice." *The modern language journal*,81 (4): 470-481.